

Pearl of the Orient Cease

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Precious place of the orient sea, Home of the majestic beings.
 Isolated land of the perpetuated beauty. Lost jewel of the past enemy.
 Imperfect aspiration from the ground. Pushed the rise of aspiring slobs.
 Patriotism is a treasure. Initiative is a venture.
 Nation loved by many.
 Embarks an interesting wonders and obscurity;
 Sacred shallow surface of beauty. The only reach the eyes can sea.
 Hospitality is a principality.
 How can a country welcome an anomaly by displaying its excellency?